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drawing by J. C. Brotze (III, 68) (Q801)

drawing by J. C. Brotze with 8 details [edit](#)

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	drawing by J. C. Brotze (III, 68)	drawing by J. C. Brotze with 8 details	
latviešu	J. K. Broces zīmējums (III, 68)	J. K. Broces zīmējums ar 8 detaļām	

Fewer languages

Statements

instance of [color plate](#) [edit](#)

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

image [edit](#)

People in streets of Riga by Brotze 72-79.jpg
1,812 × 1,918; 2.77 MB

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

Visual and Written Sources on Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries

Data Description for TextileBase

Linking Garments to Knowledge: TextileBase as an Interdisciplinary Graph for Dress and Textile Research¹

Abstract

Connected dataset:

Ieva Pigozne (2025): *Visual and Written Sources on Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries*, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16995555.

Years of creation: 2024–2025.

Institution: University of Latvia, Faculty of Humanities, Institute of Latvian History.

Funding: Grant “Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale” (LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0023), Recovery and Resilience Facility project “Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia” (5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Infrastructure provenance: The data sharing space system underlying TextileBase—from its technical architecture to its ontological design—was originally developed for the Open Music Observatory in the context of the Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) project². TextileBase was subsequently prototyped as an exploitation pathway to adapt and extend these results for cultural heritage and textile research, demonstrating their usability beyond the music domain [Open Music Europe 2023].

Keywords: dress history, Latvia, Riga, digital humanities, research data, data curation, knowledge base

Data description

This open linked dataset brings together identified visual sources depicting common people in Riga wearing **traditional clothing** or garments and accessories characteristic of traditional dress (in contrast to the more cosmopolitan European urban fashions worn by townspeople) (Welters and Lillethun 2018: 163-168).

Only a very small number of preserved items of traditional clothing from Riga survive. For this reason, visual and written sources are of particular significance (Taylor 2015: 115-146). However, since the project focuses specifically on traditional dress, as well as on the

¹ Antal, D – Pigozne, I. (2025). *Linking Garments to Knowledge: TextileBase as an Interdisciplinary Graph for Dress and Textile Research*. Preprint: [10.5281/zenodo.16914850](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16914850) [Unpublished preprint, please cite the final text and page numbering in Culture Crossroads (Vol.28) in 2025, expected publication Oct 2025 <https://culturecrossroads.lv/>]

² Open Music Europe. (2023). *Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) – An Open, Scalable, Data-to-Policy Pipeline for European Music Ecosystems*. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101095295>

clothing of the lower classes or ordinary people, the number of relevant visual and written sources is also limited. In particular, in paintings by middle-class German artists, common people rarely occupy a central place within Riga cityscapes (Tregubovs et.al. 2000).

The most important source of information is the drawings and descriptions of Johann Christoph Brotze, produced in the last three decades of the eighteenth century. Brotze depicted and described people and their clothing, often also noting their occupations and places of origin. These drawings and descriptions, written in German for his own use rather than for publication, were bound into ten large volumes known as *Sammlung verschiedener liefländischer Monumente, Prospective, Münzen, Wappen etc.* (“Collection of Various Livonian Monuments, Views, Coins, Coats of Arms etc.”). Volume I contains the series *Variety in the Streets of Riga*, while some additional depictions of people observed in Riga are included in Volumes V and VII (in the dataset, volumes are indicated with Roman numerals and page numbers with Arabic numerals, e.g. I, 59). Since most of these drawings portray and describe several individuals, the dataset contains a separate entry for each page and each person.

The albums of Brotze’s drawings and descriptions are preserved in the Library of the University of Latvia, which has published thumbnails of them. Links to these are included in the dataset; for two images the links are unfortunately not functional and could not be added.

Brotze’s drawings and descriptions of Riga and its surroundings were published between 1992 and 1996 in two volumes (Broce 1992, Broce 1996). In preparing this dataset, the Latvian descriptions were based on these published Latvian translations, with some adjustments and linguistic improvements introduced. The English translations were newly created, aiming to follow Brotze’s original style as closely as possible. In both Latvian and English descriptions, information about vehicles has been shortened, since the study of transport does not fall within the focus of this project. Researchers interested in transport history are advised to consult the original descriptions and translations.

The dataset includes those pages from Brotze’s albums in which common inhabitants of Riga are depicted. Almost all of these also contain people from middle and upper social strata, as well as individuals arriving in Riga from the countryside or abroad. All such individuals were included, even when not wearing traditional clothing, since this provides a fuller picture of the people encountered in Riga and their dress, allowing for more precise evaluation of what does and does not constitute traditional clothing and enabling comparative analysis.

The dataset also contains visual sources from the first half of the nineteenth century, including paintings and lithographs depicting ordinary people in Riga. These figures are not

always permanent inhabitants of the city, yet they contribute to the overall picture of the people encountered in Riga and their dress. These works comprise paintings by **Carl Traugott Fehhelm** (Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation) and **Johann von Radetzky** (National History Museum of Latvia), as well as lithographs by **Theodor Heinrich Rickmann** (Herder Institute, Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation), **Franz Seraph Hanfstaengl**, and **Carl Gotthard Hess** (Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation).

Some of Rickmann's lithographs from the series *Scenes from the Life of Citizens of Riga* include clarifying captions specifying the ethnic group of the people depicted, while others identify them only more generally (for example, as peasants). Discrepancies can also be observed, such as when the same lithograph is catalogued under different titles in the collections of the Herder Institute and the Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation; in such cases both variants are included. Two variants of a lithograph are also included when one was coloured and the other monochrome, or when the same work survives in two different versions with distinct inventory numbers.

In lithographs depicting specific events, such as the Midsummer Herb Market (*Zāļu tirgus*), as well as in paintings, the social or ethnic identity of the figures can often be established only by comparison with other sources where such information is given explicitly. Thus, although chronologically earlier, Brotze's drawings serve as a crucial aid in analysing nineteenth-century visual sources. Where holding institutions have made images publicly available online, links have been provided in the dataset. For lithographs without such links, the images are not available online. However, eight of Rickmann's lithographs from the Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation were published separately in an album in 2002 (Rikmans 2002). The lithographs held in the Herder Institute were not known to the publishers of this album and were therefore not included. This dataset now brings together all known lithographs of the series *Scenes from the Life of Citizens of Riga* by Rickmann in a single resource.

Description of detail

TextileBase follows the **Wikibase data model**, in which each entity is represented as an **item** (a document in a document-oriented database). Each item contains a modular dataset: a self-contained set of knowledge statements that describe everything currently known about a given visual or textual source.

Main page
Recent changes
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Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Upload file
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New item
New property
Set item sitelink
Set Item/Property label, description and aliases
Items without sitelinks
All properties
All items
Bot passwords

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

drawing by J. C. Brotze (III, 68) (Q801)

drawing by J. C. Brotze with 8 details edit

In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	drawing by J. C. Brotze (III, 68)	drawing by J. C. Brotze with 8 details	
latviešu	J. K. Broces zīmējums (III, 68)	J. K. Broces zīmējums ar 8 detaļām	

Fewer languages

Statements

instance of color plate edit

0 references

+ add reference

+ add value

image edit

People in streets of Riga by Brotze 72-79.jpg
1,812 × 1,916; 2.77 MB

0 references

+ add reference

+ add value

In archival or museological terms, this corresponds to the “level of description.” For Brotze’s drawings, the principal unit is the **colour plate** (e.g. [TXB:Q801](#)), but individual **figures or details** within a plate (e.g. [TXB:Q913](#)) are also given their own items. These are linked using **has part / part of** relationships. The entire corpus of plates ([TXB:Q769](#)) forms a higher-level item, so the structure mirrors traditional hierarchical description while remaining modular.

From the perspective of Wikibase, however, all of these are technically equivalent: each plate, figure, or volume is an item with its own statements, labels, and identifiers. The “level of description” is thus not a limitation of the data model but a decision in curatorial practice.

The screenshot shows the TextileBase interface for the entry 'a prosperous Polish Jew (detail) (Q846)'. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options, a main content area with a table of languages, a 'Statements' section, an 'Image' section, and a 'part of' section.

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	a prosperous Polish Jew (detail)	2: A prosperous Polish Jew, of the sort who comes to Riga for trade; they bring with them both various Polish goods and linen cloth. This one carries linen cloth about for sale. Detail of a drawing by J. C. Brotze (III, 55)	

Statements:

- instance of: drawing (0 references)

Image:

part of:

- drawings of J. C. Brotze (III, 55) (0 references)

For example, entry **TXB:Q846**, labelled a *prosperous Polish Jew (detail)*, is described as:

“A prosperous Polish Jew, of the sort who comes to Riga for trade; they bring with them both various Polish goods and linen cloth. This one carries linen cloth about for sale. Detail of a drawing by J. C. Brotze (III, 55).”

This entry refers to one figure from drawing III/55, while **TXB:Q788** represents the full plate on which it appears, and **TXB:Q769** identifies the entire ten-volume *Sammlung verschiedener Liefländischer Monumente....* For clarity, J. C. Brotze is added as an “inferred” creator of the individual figures, with the *stated in* property

referring to the plate.

All of these items are grouped into the **collection** *Secondary Sources of Dress and Textile History* (TXB:Q765). For the present work, we have created a **published dataset** that is a **time-stamped snapshot (2025)** of the collection, restricted to sources related to Riga. This dataset has a DOI (10.5281/zenodo.16995555) and includes 56 plates (TXB:Q788–Q843) and 123 detailed figures (TXB:Q845–Q967).

In this way, each item is simultaneously:

- a member of the collection (the ongoing research corpus), and
- a member of the published dataset (the frozen subset cited here).

This approach ensures maximum granularity, reusability, and citation stability, while preserving interoperability between human-readable description and machine-readable modular datasets. Individual entries are listed in the Annex by their label, each linked to its corresponding record in TextileBase, where the full description can be conveniently accessed.

For example, **TXB:Q801** resolves to <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Item:Q801>. Researchers who wish to fetch the data for reuse in their own systems can retrieve the same entity in multiple serializations by changing the URL to:

- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.ttl> for Turtle,

- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.nt> for N-Triples,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.rdf> for RDF/XML,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.jsonld> for JSON-LD, or
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.json> for JSON.

When using these resources, please always cite:

Ieva Pigozne (2025). *Visual and Written Sources on Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16995555.

Multimodality and copyright status of images

Johann Christoph Brotze's *Sammlung verschiedener Liefländischer Monumente, Prospecte, Münzen, Wappen etc.* is a manuscript compilation, not a printed publication of its time. The ten volumes were created in the late 18th and early 19th centuries (e.g., **Teil 1** is dated **1771**; **Teil 10** around **1806**).

At the time of creation there was no modern copyright law in the Russian Empire; the first provisions in that sense arrived with the 1828 Statute on Censorship, and a comprehensive Copyright Act followed in 1911. Given Brotze's death in 1823 and contemporary terms, the drawings and texts are public domain. The same applies to most of our other sources, too.

The most complete set of Brotze's drawings is preserved at the University of Latvia Academic Library. Online, the library provides only limited/low-resolution access (its detailed digital archive is available on the library's local network; high-resolution use generally requires permission). In our dataset we therefore link to the library previews via *described by URL* and do not embed their images.

Multiple **later reproductions** exist. Selections from the manuscripts were published in modern edited volumes in **1992**, **1996**, **2002**, and **2007**; many public-domain scans in circulation derive from these editions. Where we could visually confirm that a freely available file (e.g., on Wikimedia Commons) matches a plate in the University copy, we referenced that public-domain image under the *image* property.

This approach preserves institutional policies while adding multimodality to the dataset: the drawings function as visual sources for dress history alongside their bibliographic descriptions.

Data structure

In developing this dataset within TextileBase, we adopted a Wikibase data model that follows established semantic patterns from multiple standards. For bibliographic and textual interoperability, we draw on DCTERMS; for museum collections, on CIDOC-CRM; for archival records, on Records in Context (RiC); and for provenance, on PROV-O. We also synchronize with globally used authorities such as GeoNames for geographical reference identification and the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) for classification. This combination strikes a balance between ease of use for researchers, interoperability across disciplines, and the possibility of importing from and exporting to large GLAM systems. For further details, please refer to our forthcoming publication (currently available in preprint³).

For each visual and written source in this dataset, the following information is provided:

- holding institution
- inventory number (if specified by the museum)
- author (creator)
- title and description of the image (with Brotze's drawings accompanied by his explanatory notes)
- type of image (drawing, painting, or lithograph)
- place depicted
- date
- subject

The dating of the object is made with the *has time* property, with usually a year precision, like 1842. However, when we have only approximate dating, for example, 1770-1800, the *has time* property is qualified with an *start time* (1770) and *end time* (1800) qualifiers. In this case, the actual date entered into the database is the midpoint of the time interval with a decade or a century precision mark. In a wide interval like 1770-1800, this is displayed as 18th century (1770-1800.) The dating, if new sources allow more precise dating, can be narrowed to decade precision (in which case it is displayed, for example, as 1780s, or to a narrow start-end interval.)

Following good data management practices, we did not copy all properties to the detail item description. For Brotze's album-like plates, the "level of description" is therefore the

³ Antal, D., & Pigozne, I. (2025). *Linking Garments to Knowledge: TextileBase as an Interdisciplinary Graph for Dress and Textile Research*. In Culture Crossroads (Preprint). TextileBase. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16914850>. You can also visit our presentations Antal, D., Pigozne, I., Gábor, K., & Fredercio, A. (2025). TextileBase: Introduction. TextileBase Seminars 1, National Laboratory for Digital Humanities, ELTE, Budapest. TextileBase. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16937140>

colour plate (i.e. the page in the album), with individual figures described as subordinate details.

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TextileBase. Available: <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase> (Viewed: 10.02.2025.)

Annex

For example, **TXB:Q801** resolves to <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Item:Q801>.

Researchers who wish to fetch the data for reuse in their own systems can retrieve the same entity in multiple serializations by changing the URL to:

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- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.nt> for N-Triples,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.rdf> for RDF/XML,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.jsonld> for JSON-LD, or
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q801.json> for JSON.

Described Visual Sources

The following links provide access to their full data record, by clicking through you get a [<https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Item:Q801>](https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Item:Q801) type link that, if you need to download the data, can change according the schema above with .ttl, nt, rdf, jsonld, or json file extensions.

[drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 55\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 55\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 56\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 57\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 58, 57a\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 59\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 60\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 61\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 62\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 63\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 64\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 65\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 66\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 67\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 68\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 69\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 70\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 71\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 72\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 73\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 74\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 75\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 76\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 77\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 78\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 79\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 80\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 81\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 82\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 83\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 85\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 87\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 88\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 89\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(III, 90\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(V, 58\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(V, 122\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(V, 131\)](#) • [drawing by J. C. Brotze \(VII, 112\)](#)

[The Parade Ground on Jacob Street in front of the Arsenal \(Carl Traugott Fechhelm\)](#) • [The Town Hall Square, view from the Town Hall \(Carl Traugott Fechhelm\)](#) • [Panorama of Riga with the Pontoon Bridge constructed in 1714 \(Carl Traugott Fechhelm\)](#) • [Lithuanians at the Daugava river \(Theodor Heinrich Rickmann\)](#) • [Polish Jews in Riga \(229742\)](#) • [Polish Jews](#)

[in Riga, lithography by T. H. Rickmann \(113028b\)](#) • [Peasants and traders outside the city \(45037\)](#) • [Latvians at the Firewood Market near Riga \(VRVM 33244\)](#) • [The Herb Market in Riga \(VRVM 33246\)](#) • [The “Hunger-Kummer” \(Umurkumurs\) in Riga \(VRVM 33247\)](#) • [Peasants on the Daugava River Ice near the city gate of Riga](#) • [Peasants on the Daugava River Ice near the city gate of Riga \(VRVM 32838\)](#) • [Sailors in Āgenskalns Bay \(VRVM 33245\)](#) • [Russians in the Vegetable Gardens near Riga \(VRVM 33233\)](#) • [Peasants at the Riga Gates \(Estonians\) \(VRVM 32839\)](#) • [Riga \(Franz Seraph Hanfstaengl\)](#) • [View of Riga from Wöhrmann Garden \(Carl Gotthard Hess\)](#) • [View of Riga from the left bank of the Daugava \(Johann von Radetzky\)](#)

Details

The details are not original artefacts, they are part of Boetze’s drawings, but from a dress history perspective, they can be treated as individual sources. The following links provide access to their full data record.

[a man who arrived with a timber raft \(detail\)](#) • [a prosperous Polish Jew \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian peasant boy \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian peasant maidservant \(detail\)](#) • [a German chambermaid \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Gulbene parish in his festive dress \(detail\)](#) • [a woman of the middle class \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian selling candles and soap \(detail\)](#) • [a German girl of the middle class \(III, 56, 9.\) \(detail\)](#) • [an apprentice of a wigmaker \(detail\)](#) • [a middle class German girl \(III, 56, 11.\) \(detail\)](#) • [a small German boy of the middle class \(detail\)](#) • [a Lithuanian labourer \(detail\)](#) • [a German maidservant \(detail\)](#) • [a German woman selling pretzels \(detail\)](#) • [a German maidservant with a green shoulder shawl \(detail\)](#) • [a Jewish woman \(III, 57\) \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian merchant’s son \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian carrying vegetables \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian youth \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian nursemaid from Courland \(detail\)](#) • [a soldier of the Nasburg Regiment \(detail\)](#) • [a soldier of the Riga city guard \(detail\)](#) • [a shoemaker’s apprentice \(detail\)](#) • [a Lithuanian nobleman from Brest \(detail\)](#) • [a nobleman in the Kiev style of dress \(detail\)](#) • [the servant of a Kiev nobleman \(detail\)](#) • [a mason’s journeyman \(detail\)](#) • [a Swede of the middle class \(detail\)](#) • [a lieutenant of artillery \(detail\)](#) • [a German Jewish man \(detail\)](#) • [a non-German \[Latvian\] woman selling milk \(detail\)](#) • [two townsmen traveling on a carriage](#) • [a ferryman’s lad \(detail\)](#) • [a grenadier of the Nasburg Regiment \(detail\)](#) • [a German merchant \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian merchant \(detail\)](#) • [a non-commissioned officer of the Riga garrison \(detail\)](#) • [a young bookkeeper \(detail\)](#) • [an old wife of a Russian soldier \(detail\)](#) • [a Dutch seaman \(III, 61, 43.\) \(detail\)](#) • [a Dutch seaman \(III, 61, 44.\) \(detail\)](#) • [an Orthodox priest \(detail\)](#) • [a Orthodox cantor](#)

[\(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Dzērbene \(detail\)](#) • [a woman in Riga \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Gulbene parish \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian peasant from Gulbene parish \(detail\)](#) • [two Lithuanians \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian peasant from Mangalī \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian peasant from Vīgante manor \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Burtnieki \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant and a woman near Riga \(detail\)](#) • [two peasants from Olmūiža \(detail\)](#) • [a lieutenant or ensign of the Riga garrison \(detail\)](#) • [a woman of the higher estate \(detail\)](#) • [two labourers near the city \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant lad from the environs of the city \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant with his son from Sausnēja \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian in a fur coat \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian selling kalači \(detail\)](#) • [a soldier of the Nasburg Regiment in 1874 \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian milk-seller woman \(detail\)](#) • [a valet of a gentleman \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Drusti \(detail\)](#) • [boys' summer dress in Riga \(detail\)](#) • [boys' winter dress in Riga \(detail\)](#) • [a maidservant and a gentleman's little son \(detail\)](#) • [a wife of a Russian merchant \(III, 68\) \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Naukšēni \(detail\)](#) • [the officer's uniform in Riga \(detail\)](#) • [an officer of the Kexholm Infantry Regiment \(detail\)](#) • [a grenadier of the Kexholm Infantry Regiment \(detail\)](#) • [two peasants from Kārļakalns manor \(detail\)](#) • [a wealthy merchant's son from the Orla viceregency \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian selling herrings \(detail\)](#) • [a young Polish Jew \(detail\)](#) • [a mourning dress of persons of higher rank \(detail\)](#) • [an officer of the Imperial Russian Horse Guards \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant and a woman in summer dress \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian selling warm drinks \(detail\)](#) • [an upper class woman in summer dress \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian selling tallow candles \(detail\)](#) • [a city official \(detail\)](#) • [a wife of a Russian merchant \(III, 73\) \(detail\)](#) • [the dress of a trumpeter \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant fisherman \(detail\)](#) • [a Courland peasant boy from Baldone \(detail\)](#) • [a Courland peasant from Saules estate \(detail\)](#) • [three Lithuanians in winter dress \(detail\)](#) • [an Estonian peasant from Tarvastu \(detail\)](#) • [a Latvian peasant from Vecmuiža \(detail\)](#) • [two Latvian peasant women in winter dress \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Salaca \(detail\)](#) • [an Estonian from Lauenhof Manor \(detail\)](#) • [three peasants from Turkalne \(detail\)](#) • [an artilleryman in winter uniform \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant in winter dress from Dundaga \(detail\)](#) • [\[a man in a white coat\\] \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant and a peasant boy from Sesava \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Gostona \(detail\)](#) • [a young Cossack from Ukraine \(detail\)](#) • [a Dessau philanthropist \(detail\)](#) • [a woman from Ruhnu Island \(detail\)](#) • [two peasants from Ruhnu Island \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant from Palsmane \(detail\)](#) • [two Russian carpenters \(detail\)](#) • [a Greek woman from Morea \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian maiden who sells lemons \(detail\)](#) • [a Russian gardener's lad \(detail\)](#) • [wife of a Latvian peasant from Turkalne \(detail\)](#) • [a Bashkir from Finland \(detail\)](#) • [a soldier of the Orenburg Infantry Regiment \(detail\)](#) • [a grenadier of the Keksholm Infantry Regiment \(detail\)](#) • [Latvian maidens in festive dress \(detail\)](#) • [a Cossack \(detail\)](#) • [a Bashkir \(detail\)](#) • [a peasant maiden and woman from Lielvārde \(detail\)](#) • [a sergeant](#)

of the Pskov Dragoon Regiment, front view (detail) • a sergeant of the Pskov Dragoon Regiment, back view (detail)